

CGMega_Docker_Tutorials

Please follow the guide below to install and test CGMega_docker.

System Requirements

CGMega_docker image was tested on Ubuntu 22.04. We do not recommend using WSL or VMware to test this docker image as the computation requires GPU acceleration or its calculation may be extremely slow. It is recommended that GPU memory should be more than 24 GB.

The Docker had been tested in the following two conditions:

Computer	1	2
System	Ubuntu 22.04.03 LTS	Ubuntu 20.04 LTS
CPU	Intel(R) Xeon(R) W-2225 CPU @ 4.10GHz 4.10 GHz	Intel(R) Xeon(R) Silver 4210R CPU @ 2.40GHz
GPU	NVIDIA RTX A6000, 48G	NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090, 24G
NVIDIA	515.65.01	470.74
CUDA	11.7	11.4

Docker_Download

There are three major steps to download docker:

- enable the Docker software source
- import the GPG key
- install the package

Update the package index and install the necessary dependencies to add a new HTTPS software source in linux terminal:

```
sudo apt update
```

```
root@ThinkStation:/home/psy# sudo apt update
Get:1 http://security.ubuntu.com/ubuntu jammy-security InRelease [110 kB]
Hit:2 http://mirrors.tuna.tsinghua.edu.cn/ubuntu jammy InRelease
Hit:3 http://mirrors.tuna.tsinghua.edu.cn/ubuntu jammy-updates InRelease
Hit:4 http://mirrors.tuna.tsinghua.edu.cn/ubuntu jammy-backports InRelease
Fetched 110 kB in 3s (33.6 kB/s)
Reading package lists... Done
Building dependency tree... Done
Reading state information... Done
440 packages can be upgraded. Run 'apt list --upgradable' to see them.
```

```
sudo apt install apt-transport-https ca-certificates curl gnupg-agent software-properties-common
```

Choose y to continue

```
root@ThinkStation:/home/psy# sudo apt install apt-transport-https ca-certificates curl gnupg-agent software-properties-common
Reading package lists... Done
Building dependency tree... Done
Reading state information... Done
The following package was automatically installed and is no longer required:
  systemd-hwe-hwdb
Use 'sudo apt autoremove' to remove it.
The following additional packages will be installed:
  libcurl4 python3-software-properties software-properties-gtk
  ubuntu-advantage-tools
Recommended packages:
  ubuntu-pro-client-l10n
The following NEW packages will be installed:
  apt-transport-https curl gnupg-agent
The following packages will be upgraded:
  ca-certificates libcurl4 python3-software-properties
  software-properties-common software-properties-gtk ubuntu-advantage-tools
6 upgraded, 3 newly installed, 0 to remove and 434 not upgraded.
Need to get 519 kB/965 kB of archives.
After this operation, 690 kB disk space will be freed.
Do you want to continue? [Y/n] y
```

Installation complete

```
Selecting previously unselected package curl.
Preparing to unpack .../4-curl_7.81.0-1ubuntu1.14_amd64.deb ...
Unpacking curl (7.81.0-1ubuntu1.14) ...
Selecting previously unselected package gnupg-agent.
Preparing to unpack .../5-gnupg-agent_2.2.27-3ubuntu2.1_all.deb ...
Unpacking gnupg-agent (2.2.27-3ubuntu2.1) ...
Preparing to unpack .../6-software-properties-common_0.99.22.7_all.deb ...
Unpacking software-properties-common (0.99.22.7) over (0.99.22.2) ...
Preparing to unpack .../7-software-properties-gtk_0.99.22.7_all.deb ...
Unpacking software-properties-gtk (0.99.22.7) over (0.99.22.2) ...
Preparing to unpack .../8-python3-software-properties_0.99.22.7_all.deb ...
Unpacking python3-software-properties (0.99.22.7) over (0.99.22.2) ...
Setting up apt-transport-https (2.4.11) ...
Setting up ca-certificates (20230311ubuntu0.22.04.1) ...
Updating certificates in /etc/ssl/certs...
rehash: warning: skipping ca-certificates.crt,it does not contain exactly one certificate or CRL
19 added, 9 removed; done.
Setting up python3-software-properties (0.99.22.7) ...
Setting up gnupg-agent (2.2.27-3ubuntu2.1) ...
Setting up libcurl4:amd64 (7.81.0-1ubuntu1.14) ...
Setting up curl (7.81.0-1ubuntu1.14) ...
Setting up ubuntu-advantage-tools (30~22.04) ...
Installing new version of config file /etc/apt/apt.conf.d/20apt-esm-hook.conf ...
Installing new version of config file /etc/ubuntu-advantage/uaclient.conf ...
Installing new version of config file /etc/update-motd.d/91-contract-ua-esm-status ...
Removing obsolete conffile /etc/update-motd.d/88-esm-announce ...
Removing obsolete conffile /etc/ubuntu-advantage/help_data.yaml ...
Setting up software-properties-common (0.99.22.7) ...
Setting up software-properties-gtk (0.99.22.7) ...
Processing triggers for dbus (1.12.20-2ubuntu4) ...
Processing triggers for shared-mime-info (2.1-2) ...
Processing triggers for mailcap (3.70+nmu1ubuntu1) ...
Processing triggers for desktop-file-utils (0.26-1ubuntu3) ...
Processing triggers for hicolor-icon-theme (0.17-2) ...
Processing triggers for gnome-menus (3.36.0-1ubuntu3) ...
Processing triggers for libglib2.0-0:amd64 (2.72.1-1) ...
Processing triggers for libc-bin (2.35-0ubuntu3.1) ...
Processing triggers for man-db (2.10.2-1) ...
Processing triggers for ca-certificates (20230311ubuntu0.22.04.1) ...
Updating certificates in /etc/ssl/certs...
0 added, 0 removed; done.
Running hooks in /etc/ca-certificates/update.d...
done.
root@ThinkStation:/home/psy#
```

Import the GPG key of the source repository using the following curl:

```
curl -fsSL https://download.docker.com/linux/ubuntu/gpg | sudo apt-key add -
```

Press Enter to continue

```
root@ThinkStation:/home/psy# sudo add-apt-repository "deb [arch=amd64] https://download.docker.com/linux/ubuntu $(lsb_release -cs) stable"
Repository: 'deb [arch=amd64] https://download.docker.com/linux/ubuntu jammy stable'
Description:
Archive for codename: jammy components: stable
More info: https://download.docker.com/linux/ubuntu
Adding repository.
Press [ENTER] to continue or Ctrl-C to cancel.
Adding deb entry to /etc/apt/sources.list.d/archive_url-https_download_docker_com_linux_ubuntu_jammy.list
Adding disabled deb-src entry to /etc/apt/sources.list.d/archive_url-https_download_docker_com_linux_ubuntu_jammy.list
Hit:1 https://security.ubuntu.com/ubuntu jammy-security InRelease
Get:2 https://download.docker.com/linux/ubuntu jammy InRelease [48.8 kB]
Get:3 https://download.docker.com/linux/ubuntu jammy/stable amd64 Packages [22.7 kB]
Hit:4 https://mirrors.tuna.tsinghua.edu.cn/ubuntu jammy InRelease
Hit:5 http://mirrors.tuna.tsinghua.edu.cn/ubuntu jammy-updates InRelease
Hit:6 http://mirrors.tuna.tsinghua.edu.cn/ubuntu jammy-backports InRelease
Fetched 71.5 kB in 4s (20.4 kB/s)
Reading package lists... Done
W: https://download.docker.com/linux/ubuntu/dists/jammy/InRelease: Key is stored in legacy trusted.gpg keyring (/etc/apt/trusted.gpg), see the DEPRECATION section in apt-key(8) for details.
root@ThinkStation:/home/psy#
```

Add the Docker APT software source to your system:

```
sudo add-apt-repository "deb [arch=amd64]
https://download.docker.com/linux/ubuntu $(lsb_release -cs) stable"
```

Press Enter to continue

```
root@thinkstation:/home/psy# sudo add-apt-repository "deb [arch=amd64] https://download.docker.com/linux/ubuntu $(lsb_release -cs) stable"
Repository: 'deb [arch=amd64] https://download.docker.com/linux/ubuntu jammy stable'
Description:
Archive for codename: jammy components: stable
More info: https://download.docker.com/linux/ubuntu
Adding repository.
Press [ENTER] to continue or Ctrl-C to cancel.
Adding deb entry to /etc/apt/sources.list.d/archive_url-https_download_docker_com_linux_ubuntu-jammy.list
Adding disabled deb-src entry to /etc/apt/sources.list.d/archive_url-https_download_docker_com_linux_ubuntu-jammy.list
Hit:1 http://security.ubuntu.com/ubuntu jammy-security InRelease
Get:2 https://download.docker.com/linux/ubuntu jammy InRelease [48.8 kB]
Get:3 https://download.docker.com/linux/ubuntu jammy/stable amd64 Packages [22.7 kB]
Hit:4 http://mirrors.tuna.tsinghua.edu.cn/ubuntu jammy InRelease
Hit:5 https://mirrors.tuna.tsinghua.edu.cn/ubuntu jammy-updates InRelease
Hit:6 http://mirrors.tuna.tsinghua.edu.cn/ubuntu jammy-backports InRelease
Fetched 71.5 kB in 4s (20.4 kB/s)
Reading package lists... Done
W: https://download.docker.com/linux/ubuntu/dists/jammy/InRelease: Key is stored in legacy trusted.gpg keyring (/etc/apt/trusted.gpg), see the DEPRECATION section in apt-key(8) for details.
```

Install the latest version of docker

```
sudo apt update
sudo apt install docker-ce docker-ce-cli containerd.io
```

Choose y to continue

```
root@thinkstation:/home/psy# sudo apt update
sudo apt install docker-ce docker-ce-cli containerd.io
Hit:1 https://download.docker.com/linux/ubuntu jammy InRelease
Hit:2 http://security.ubuntu.com/ubuntu jammy-security InRelease
Hit:3 http://mirrors.tuna.tsinghua.edu.cn/ubuntu jammy InRelease
Hit:4 http://mirrors.tuna.tsinghua.edu.cn/ubuntu jammy-updates InRelease
Hit:5 https://mirrors.tuna.tsinghua.edu.cn/ubuntu jammy-backports InRelease
Reading package lists... Done
Building dependency tree... Done
Reading state information... Done
434 packages can be upgraded. Run 'apt list --upgradable' to see them.
W: https://download.docker.com/linux/ubuntu/dists/jammy/InRelease: Key is stored in legacy trusted.gpg keyring (/etc/apt/trusted.gpg), see the DEPRECATION section in apt-key(8) for details.
Reading package lists... Done
Building dependency tree... Done
Reading state information... Done
The following package was automatically installed and is no longer required:
  systemd-hwdb
Use 'sudo apt autoremove' to remove it.
The following additional packages will be installed:
  docker-buildx-plugin docker-ce-rootless-extras docker-compose-plugin git git-man liberror-perl libsrlp0 pigz slirp4netns
Suggested packages:
  aufs-tools cgroupfs-mount | cgroup-lite git-daemon-run | git-daemon-sysvinit git-doc git-email git-gui gitk gitweb git-cvs git-mediawiki git-svn
The following NEW packages will be installed:
  containerd.io docker-buildx-plugin docker-ce docker-ce-cli docker-ce-rootless-extras docker-compose-plugin git git-man liberror-perl libsrlp0 pigz slirp4netns
8 upgraded, 12 newly installed, 0 to remove and 434 not upgraded.
Need to get 118 MB of archives.
After this operation, 430 MB of additional disk space will be used.
Do you want to continue? [Y/n]
```

Installation is complete

```
Preparing to unpack .../03-docker-ce-cli_5%3a24.0.7-1~ubuntu.22.04~jammy_amd64.deb ...
Unpacking docker-ce-cli (5:24.0.7-1~ubuntu.22.04~jammy) ...
Selecting previously unselected package docker-ce.
Preparing to unpack .../04-docker-ce_5%3a24.0.7-1~ubuntu.22.04~jammy_amd64.deb ...
Unpacking docker-ce (5:24.0.7-1~ubuntu.22.04~jammy) ...
Selecting previously unselected package docker-ce-rootless-extras.
Preparing to unpack .../05-docker-ce-rootless-extras_5%3a24.0.7-1~ubuntu.22.04~jammy_amd64.deb ...
Unpacking docker-ce-rootless-extras (5:24.0.7-1~ubuntu.22.04~jammy) ...
Selecting previously unselected package docker-compose-plugin.
Preparing to unpack .../06-docker-compose-plugin_2.21.0-1~ubuntu.22.04~jammy_amd64.deb ...
Unpacking docker-compose-plugin (2.21.0-1~ubuntu.22.04~jammy) ...
Selecting previously unselected package liberror-perl.
Preparing to unpack .../07-liberror-perl_0.17029-1_all.deb ...
Unpacking liberror-perl (0.17029-1) ...
Selecting previously unselected package git-man.
Preparing to unpack .../08-git-man_1%3a2.34.1-1ubuntu1.10_all.deb ...
Unpacking git-man (1:2.34.1-1ubuntu1.10) ...
Selecting previously unselected package git.
Preparing to unpack .../09-git_1%3a2.34.1-1ubuntu1.10_amd64.deb ...
Unpacking git (1:2.34.1-1ubuntu1.10) ...
Selecting previously unselected package libslirp0:amd64.
Preparing to unpack .../10-libslirp0_4.6.1-1build1_amd64.deb ...
Unpacking libslirp0:amd64 (4.6.1-1build1) ...
Selecting previously unselected package slirp4netns.
Preparing to unpack .../11-slirp4netns_1.0.1-2_amd64.deb ...
Unpacking slirp4netns (1.0.1-2) ...
Setting up liberror-perl (0.17029-1) ...
Setting up docker-buildx-plugin (0.11.2-1~ubuntu.22.04~jammy) ...
Setting up containerd.io (1.6.24-1) ...
Created symlink /etc/systemd/system/multi-user.target.wants/containerd.service → /lib/systemd/system/containerd.service.
Setting up docker-compose-plugin (2.21.0-1~ubuntu.22.04~jammy) ...
Setting up docker-ce-cli (5:24.0.7-1~ubuntu.22.04~jammy) ...
Setting up libslirp0:amd64 (4.6.1-1build1) ...
Setting up pigz (2.6-1) ...
Setting up git-man (1:2.34.1-1ubuntu1.10) ...
Setting up docker-ce-rootless-extras (5:24.0.7-1~ubuntu.22.04~jammy) ...
Setting up slirp4netns (1.0.1-2) ...
Setting up docker-ce (5:24.0.7-1~ubuntu.22.04~jammy) ...
Created symlink /etc/systemd/system/multi-user.target.wants/docker.service → /lib/systemd/system/docker.service.
Created symlink /etc/systemd/system/sockets.target.wants/docker.socket → /lib/systemd/system/docker.socket.
Setting up git (1:2.34.1-1ubuntu1.10) ...
Processing triggers for man-db (2.10.2-1) ...
Processing triggers for libc-bin (2.35-0ubuntu3.1) ...
root@ThinkStation:/home/psy#
```

You can verify it using the following command after installation is complete:

```
sudo systemctl status docker
```

The output will look like this (ctrl + c to exit):

```
root@psy-ThinkStation-P520:/home/psy# sudo systemctl status docker
● docker.service - Docker Application Container Engine
   Loaded: loaded (/lib/systemd/system/docker.service; enabled; vendor preset:
   Active: active (running) since Tue 2023-11-21 09:38:27 CST; 1min 3s ago
   TriggeredBy: ● docker.socket
     Docs: https://docs.docker.com
    Main PID: 22117 (dockerd)
       Tasks: 13
      Memory: 25.2M
         CPU: 156ms
    CGroup: /system.slice/docker.service
           └─22117 /usr/bin/dockerd -H fd:// --containerd=/run/containerd/con>

11月 21 09:38:27 psy-ThinkStation-P520 systemd[1]: Starting Docker Application >
11月 21 09:38:27 psy-ThinkStation-P520 dockerd[22117]: time="2023-11-21T09:38:2>
11月 21 09:38:27 psy-ThinkStation-P520 systemd[1]: Started Docker Application C>
lines 1-22/22 (END)
```

If you face the problem of active: failed (Result:exit-code), you can try following command to fix it:

```
sudo service docker restart
```

```
root@xiangmeida:/home/xiangmeida# sudo systemctl status docker
* docker.service - Docker Application Container Engine
   Loaded: loaded (/lib/systemd/system/docker.service; enabled; vendor preset: enabled)
   Active: failed (Result: exit-code) since Fri 2023-11-24 09:52:38 CST; 7s ago
   TriggeredBy: * docker.socket
     Docs: https://docs.docker.com
    Process: 25922 ExecStart=/usr/bin/dockerd -H fd:// --containerd=/run/containerd/containerd.sock (code=exited, status=1/FAILURE)
    Main PID: 25922 (code=exited, status=1/FAILURE)
         CPU: 155ms

11月 24 09:52:38 xiangmeida systemd[1]: docker.service: Scheduled restart job, restart counter is at 3.
11月 24 09:52:38 xiangmeida systemd[1]: Stopped Docker Application Container Engine.
11月 24 09:52:38 xiangmeida systemd[1]: docker.service: Start request repeated too quickly.
11月 24 09:52:38 xiangmeida systemd[1]: docker.service: Failed with result 'exit-code'.
11月 24 09:52:38 xiangmeida systemd[1]: Failed to start Docker Application Container Engine.
```

You can execute the docker command without sudo. Run a test container to check docker installation:

```
docker container run hello-world
```

```
root@psy-ThinkStation-P520:/home/psy# docker container run hello-world
Unable to find image 'hello-world:latest' locally
latest: Pulling from library/hello-world
719385e32844: Pull complete
Digest: sha256:c79d06dfdfd3d3eb04cafd0dc2bacab0992ebc243e083cabe208bac4dd7759e0
Status: Downloaded newer image for hello-world:latest

Hello from Docker!
This message shows that your installation appears to be working correctly.

To generate this message, Docker took the following steps:
 1. The Docker client contacted the Docker daemon.
 2. The Docker daemon pulled the "hello-world" image from the Docker Hub.
    (amd64)
 3. The Docker daemon created a new container from that image which runs the
    executable that produces the output you are currently reading.
 4. The Docker daemon streamed that output to the Docker client, which sent it
    to your terminal.

To try something more ambitious, you can run an Ubuntu container with:
$ docker run -it ubuntu bash

Share images, automate workflows, and more with a free Docker ID:
https://hub.docker.com/

For more examples and ideas, visit:
https://docs.docker.com/get-started/

root@psy-ThinkStation-P520:/home/psy#
```

If you have any problems with the docker installation, you can click this link for detailed information. ([Get Docker](#) | [Docker Docs](#))

Install NVIDIA container toolkit

NVIDIA container toolkit is used for GPU acceleration, execute the following two sets of commands to install

1. Configure the repository:

```
curl -fsSL https://nvidia.github.io/libnvidia-container/gpgkey | sudo gpg --dearmor -o /usr/share/keyrings/nvidia-container-toolkit-keyring.gpg \

&& curl -s -L https://nvidia.github.io/libnvidia-container/stable/deb/nvidia-container-toolkit.list | \

sed 's#deb https://#deb [signed-by=/usr/share/keyrings/nvidia-container-toolkit-keyring.gpg] https://#g' | \

sudo tee /etc/apt/sources.list.d/nvidia-container-toolkit.list \

&& \

sudo apt-get update
```

The results are shown as follows

```
root@thinkstation:/home/psy# curl -fsSL https://nvidia.github.io/libnvidia-container/gpgkey | sudo gpg --dearmor -o /usr/share/keyrings/nvidia-container-toolkit-keyring.gpg \
&& curl -s -L https://nvidia.github.io/libnvidia-container/stable/deb/nvidia-container-toolkit.list | \
sed 's#deb https://#deb [signed-by=/usr/share/keyrings/nvidia-container-toolkit-keyring.gpg] https://#g' | \
sudo tee /etc/apt/sources.list.d/nvidia-container-toolkit.list \
&& \
sudo apt-get update
deb [signed-by=/usr/share/keyrings/nvidia-container-toolkit-keyring.gpg] https://nvidia.github.io/libnvidia-container/stable/deb/$ARCH /
deb [signed-by=/usr/share/keyrings/nvidia-container-toolkit-keyring.gpg] https://nvidia.github.io/libnvidia-container/experimental/deb/$ARCH /
Hit:1 https://download.docker.com/linux/ubuntu jammy InRelease
Hit:2 http://security.ubuntu.com/ubuntu jammy-security InRelease
Hit:3 http://mirrors.tuna.tsinghua.edu.cn/ubuntu jammy InRelease
Hit:4 http://mirrors.tuna.tsinghua.edu.cn/ubuntu jammy-updates InRelease
Hit:5 http://mirrors.tuna.tsinghua.edu.cn/ubuntu jammy-backports InRelease
Get:6 https://nvidia.github.io/libnvidia-container/stable/deb/amd64 InRelease [1,477 B]
Get:7 https://nvidia.github.io/libnvidia-container/stable/deb/amd64 Packages [5,376 B]
Fetched 6,853 B in 9s (750 B/s)
Reading package lists... Done
W: https://download.docker.com/linux/ubuntu/dists/jammy/InRelease: Key is stored in legacy trusted.gpg keyring (/etc/apt/trusted.gpg), see the DEPRECATION section in apt-key(8) for details.
```

2. Install the NVIDIA Container Toolkit packages:

```
sudo apt-get install -y nvidia-container-toolkit
```

```
root@ThinkStation:/home/psy# sudo apt-get install -y nvidia-container-toolkit
Reading package lists... Done
Building dependency tree... Done
Reading state information... Done
The following package was automatically installed and is no longer required:
  systemd-hwe-hwdb
Use 'sudo apt autoremove' to remove it.
The following additional packages will be installed:
  libnvidia-container-tools libnvidia-container1 nvidia-container-toolkit-base
The following NEW packages will be installed:
  libnvidia-container-tools libnvidia-container1 nvidia-container-toolkit nvidia-container-toolkit-base
0 upgraded, 4 newly installed, 0 to remove and 434 not upgraded.
Need to get 4,194 kB of archives.
After this operation, 16.6 MB of additional disk space will be used.
Get:1 https://nvidia.github.io/libnvidia-container/stable/deb/amd64 libnvidia-container1 1.14.3-1 [923 kB]
9% [1 libnvidia-container1 451 kB/923 kB 49%]

3min 489% [1 libnvidia-container1 468 kB/923 kB 51%]
Get:2 https://nvidia.github.io/libnvidia-container/stable/deb/amd64 libnvidia-container-tools 1.14.3-1 [19.3 kB]
Get:3 https://nvidia.github.io/libnvidia-container/stable/deb/amd64 nvidia-container-toolkit-base 1.14.3-1 [2,336 kB]
Get:4 https://nvidia.github.io/libnvidia-container/stable/deb/amd64 nvidia-container-toolkit 1.14.3-1 [917 kB]
Fetched 4,194 kB in 7min 0s (9,976 B/s)
Selecting previously unselected package libnvidia-container1:amd64.
(Reading database ... 198189 files and directories currently installed.)
Preparing to unpack .../libnvidia-container1_1.14.3-1_amd64.deb ...
Unpacking libnvidia-container1:amd64 (1.14.3-1) ...
Selecting previously unselected package libnvidia-container-tools.
Preparing to unpack .../libnvidia-container-tools_1.14.3-1_amd64.deb ...
Unpacking libnvidia-container-tools (1.14.3-1) ...
Selecting previously unselected package nvidia-container-toolkit-base.
Preparing to unpack .../nvidia-container-toolkit-base_1.14.3-1_amd64.deb ...
Unpacking nvidia-container-toolkit-base (1.14.3-1) ...
Selecting previously unselected package nvidia-container-toolkit.
Preparing to unpack .../nvidia-container-toolkit_1.14.3-1_amd64.deb ...
Unpacking nvidia-container-toolkit (1.14.3-1) ...
Setting up nvidia-container-toolkit-base (1.14.3-1) ...
Setting up libnvidia-container1:amd64 (1.14.3-1) ...
Setting up libnvidia-container-tools (1.14.3-1) ...
Setting up nvidia-container-toolkit (1.14.3-1) ...
Processing triggers for libc-bin (2.35-0ubuntu3.1) ...
```

When the installation is finished, you can verify the installation by entering the following command:

```
nvidia-container-cli -k -d /dev/tty info
```

```
root@ThinkStation:/home/psy# nvidia-container-cli -k -d /dev/tty info
-- WARNING, the following logs are for debugging purposes only --
I1121 06:44:37.166483 14234 nvc.c:376] initializing library context (version=1.14.3, build=1eb5a30a6ad0415550a9df632ac8832bf7e2bbba)
I1121 06:44:37.166549 14234 nvc.c:350] using root /
I1121 06:44:37.166556 14234 nvc.c:351] using ldcache /etc/ld.so.cache
I1121 06:44:37.166559 14234 nvc.c:352] using unprivileged user 65534:65534
I1121 06:44:37.166582 14234 nvc.c:393] attempting to load dxcore to see if we are running under Windows Subsystem for Linux (WSL)
I1121 06:44:37.166757 14234 nvc.c:395] dxcore initialization failed, continuing assuming a non-WSL environment
W1121 06:44:37.171876 14234 nvc.c:258] failed to detect NVIDIA devices
I1121 06:44:37.172119 14235 nvc.c:278] loading kernel module nvidia
E1121 06:44:37.178905 14235 nvc.c:280] could not load kernel module nvidia
I1121 06:44:37.178927 14235 nvc.c:296] loading kernel module nvidia_uvm
E1121 06:44:37.184206 14235 nvc.c:298] could not load kernel module nvidia_uvm
I1121 06:44:37.184225 14235 nvc.c:305] loading kernel module nvidia_modeset
E1121 06:44:37.188992 14235 nvc.c:307] could not load kernel module nvidia_modeset
I1121 06:44:37.189340 14236 rpc.c:71] starting driver rpc service
I1121 06:44:37.189862 14234 rpc.c:135] driver rpc service terminated with signal 15
nvidia-container-cli: initialization error: load library failed: libnvidia-ml.so.1: cannot open shared object file: no such file or directory
I1121 06:44:37.189918 14234 nvc.c:434] shutting down library context
```

For more information about how to install NVIDIA container toolkit, click here [NVIDIA Container Toolkit](#)

Run CGMega_Docker image

1. Decompress the compressed package to obtain an image package in.tar format

```
tar -zxvf cgmega.tar.gz
```

If the docker you get is in tar file format, you can skip to the second step to load the image. For the purpose of decompressing gz or loading image, `cd` command is required to go into the correct path contained the tar package or gz package.

For instance, suppose that your file is in the document folder, you can run such command:

```
cd Document/
```

Check files in the folder with `ls` command:

```
root@psy-ThinkStation-P520:/home/psy/Document# ls
cgmega_second_edition.tar  cgmega.tar  -f
```

2. Load image

```
sudo docker load -i cgmega.tar
```

```
root@psy-ThinkStation-P520:/home/psy/Document# sudo docker load -i cgmega.tar
6babb56be259: Loading layer [=====>] 65.51MB/65.51MB
01fd15897b73: Loading layer [=====>] 17.1MB/17.1MB
08cefe1507aa: Loading layer [=====>] 34.31MB/34.31MB
982020adacf1: Loading layer [=====>] 3.072kB/3.072kB
c34d2d5e46fb: Loading layer [=====>] 17.92kB/17.92kB
12f3f98351b3: Loading layer [=====>] 1.736GB/1.736GB
0e01f79eed8b: Loading layer [=====>] 261.6kB/261.6kB
53864c8a1793: Loading layer [=====>] 2.368GB/2.368GB
51ac37be8b58: Loading layer [=====>] 373.2kB/373.2kB
d8de99759afa: Loading layer [=====>] 4.016GB/4.016GB
549885212e9a: Loading layer [=====>] 4.712MB/4.712MB
1812227fc102: Loading layer [=====>] 6.197GB/6.197GB
82b2a0271b66: Loading layer [=====>] 1.536kB/1.536kB
c9e7d91144c0: Loading layer [=====>] 2.048kB/2.048kB
87d4f78a0b13: Loading layer [=====>] 52.22kB/52.22kB
90ba9c342a9f: Loading layer [=====>] 126.2MB/126.2MB
131e4e56e2f9: Loading layer [=====>] 17.93MB/17.93MB
8ba5c730b05f: Loading layer [=====>] 189.6MB/189.6MB
1f2ba813114f: Loading layer [=====>] 411MB/411MB
8ab56de91c7c: Loading layer [=====>] 2.26GB/2.26GB
Loaded image: cgmega:latest
```

3. Check whether the image is successfully loaded

```
sudo docker images
```

```
root@psy-ThinkStation-P520:/home/psy/Document# sudo docker images
REPOSITORY          TAG             IMAGE ID        CREATED         SIZE
cgmega              latest         665fd6b234bb   5 weeks ago    17.4GB
hello-world         latest         9c7a54a9a43c   6 months ago   13.3kB
```

4. Run docker image (use `ls` to check the files in the container after running)

```
docker run -it --gpus all --name=" cgmega_test" cgmega /bin/bash
```

```
root@psy-ThinkStation-P520:/home/psy/Document# docker run -it --gpus all --name=" cgmega_test" cgmega /bin/bash
root@f38e6c2518ff:/CGMega# ls
Dockerfile  LICENSE  README.md  Tutorial.ipynb  config.yaml  config_load.py  data  data_preprocess_cv.py  explain  explain_pyg.py  explainer.py  img  main.py  model.py  outls  predict  utils.py
```

5. Run the python file named main.py in the container to train the model

```
python main.py -g 0
```

Start training:

```
root@cc38a5d05d8f:/CGMega# python main.py -g 0
Loading Hi-C matrix from data/Breast_Cancer_Matrix/MCF7_Hi-C_Ice .....
Loading PPI matrix from data/CPDB/CPDB_matrix.csv .....
Feature matrix shape: (16165, 15)
Number of edges: 547530, Dimensionality of edge: 1,
Number of nodes: 16165
Finished! Saving dataset to data/Breast_Cancer_Matrix/MCF7_CPDB_dataset.pkl .....
Doing below distrubs:
{'add': [], 'remove': [], 'random': []}
Drop 0.5 of negative train samples and 0.0 of positive train samples
Negatives: 534, Positives: 241
Start Training
Train AUPRC: 0.6945, AUROC: 0.8309, ACC: 0.7368
Train AUPRC: 0.7113, AUROC: 0.8498, ACC: 0.7858
Train AUPRC: 0.7294, AUROC: 0.8674, ACC: 0.8219
Train AUPRC: 0.7502, AUROC: 0.8876, ACC: 0.8155
Train AUPRC: 0.7807, AUROC: 0.9034, ACC: 0.8258
Train AUPRC: 0.8003, AUROC: 0.9104, ACC: 0.8348
Train AUPRC: 0.8151, AUROC: 0.9165, ACC: 0.8361
Train AUPRC: 0.8242, AUROC: 0.9203, ACC: 0.8361
Train AUPRC: 0.8315, AUROC: 0.9239, ACC: 0.8413
Train AUPRC: 0.8368, AUROC: 0.9253, ACC: 0.8271
Epoch: 9, Train loss: 0.4835, Acc: 0.7862, Auprc: 0.6609, TP: 25, F1: 0.6173, Auroc: 0.9096
Train AUPRC: 0.8428, AUROC: 0.9293, ACC: 0.8439
Train AUPRC: 0.8441, AUROC: 0.9326, ACC: 0.8219
Train AUPRC: 0.8459, AUROC: 0.9341, ACC: 0.8194
Train AUPRC: 0.8587, AUROC: 0.9387, ACC: 0.8658
Train AUPRC: 0.8724, AUROC: 0.9424, ACC: 0.8503
Train AUPRC: 0.8708, AUROC: 0.9428, ACC: 0.8877
Train AUPRC: 0.8737, AUROC: 0.9442, ACC: 0.8413
Train AUPRC: 0.8727, AUROC: 0.9431, ACC: 0.8194
Train AUPRC: 0.8884, AUROC: 0.9473, ACC: 0.8826
Train AUPRC: 0.8905, AUROC: 0.9483, ACC: 0.8890
Epoch: 19, Train loss: 0.3600, Acc: 0.8207, Auprc: 0.7232, TP: 23, F1: 0.6389, Auroc: 0.9203
Train AUPRC: 0.8960, AUROC: 0.9502, ACC: 0.8787
Train AUPRC: 0.8845, AUROC: 0.9487, ACC: 0.9071
Train AUPRC: 0.9018, AUROC: 0.9523, ACC: 0.8865
```

Training completed:

```
Train AUPRC: 0.9722, AUROC: 0.9825, ACC: 0.9471
Epoch: 419, Train loss: 0.1740, Acc: 0.8828, Auprc: 0.9083, TP: 24, F1: 0.7385, Auroc: 0.9692
Train AUPRC: 0.9723, AUROC: 0.9826, ACC: 0.9484
Train AUPRC: 0.9723, AUROC: 0.9826, ACC: 0.9484
Train AUPRC: 0.9724, AUROC: 0.9827, ACC: 0.9471
Train AUPRC: 0.9724, AUROC: 0.9827, ACC: 0.9484
Train AUPRC: 0.9725, AUROC: 0.9827, ACC: 0.9471
Train AUPRC: 0.9724, AUROC: 0.9827, ACC: 0.9471
Train AUPRC: 0.9724, AUROC: 0.9827, ACC: 0.9471
Train AUPRC: 0.9724, AUROC: 0.9827, ACC: 0.9471
Train AUPRC: 0.9723, AUROC: 0.9826, ACC: 0.9471
Train AUPRC: 0.9726, AUROC: 0.9827, ACC: 0.9471
Train AUPRC: 0.9724, AUROC: 0.9826, ACC: 0.9471
Epoch: 429, Train loss: 0.2598, Acc: 0.8828, Auprc: 0.9083, TP: 24, F1: 0.7385, Auroc: 0.9692
Train AUPRC: 0.9724, AUROC: 0.9827, ACC: 0.9484
Train AUPRC: 0.9723, AUROC: 0.9826, ACC: 0.9471
Train AUPRC: 0.9724, AUROC: 0.9827, ACC: 0.9484
Train AUPRC: 0.9722, AUROC: 0.9826, ACC: 0.9471
Train AUPRC: 0.9723, AUROC: 0.9826, ACC: 0.9484
Train AUPRC: 0.9723, AUROC: 0.9826, ACC: 0.9471
Train AUPRC: 0.9724, AUROC: 0.9826, ACC: 0.9471
Train AUPRC: 0.9724, AUROC: 0.9826, ACC: 0.9471
Train AUPRC: 0.9724, AUROC: 0.9827, ACC: 0.9484
Train AUPRC: 0.9724, AUROC: 0.9827, ACC: 0.9484
Train AUPRC: 0.9724, AUROC: 0.9827, ACC: 0.9471
Epoch: 439, Train loss: 0.1577, Acc: 0.8828, Auprc: 0.9083, TP: 24, F1: 0.7385, Auroc: 0.9692
Train AUPRC: 0.9724, AUROC: 0.9827, ACC: 0.9471
Train AUPRC: 0.9725, AUROC: 0.9827, ACC: 0.9484
Train AUPRC: 0.9723, AUROC: 0.9826, ACC: 0.9484
Train AUPRC: 0.9724, AUROC: 0.9827, ACC: 0.9484
Train AUPRC: 0.9724, AUROC: 0.9827, ACC: 0.9484
Train AUPRC: 0.9723, AUROC: 0.9827, ACC: 0.9471
Train AUPRC: 0.9723, AUROC: 0.9826, ACC: 0.9458
Train AUPRC: 0.9724, AUROC: 0.9827, ACC: 0.9471
Train AUPRC: 0.9723, AUROC: 0.9826, ACC: 0.9471
Train AUPRC: 0.9723, AUROC: 0.9826, ACC: 0.9471
Epoch: 449, Train loss: 0.1392, Acc: 0.8828, Auprc: 0.9083, TP: 24, F1: 0.7385, Auroc: 0.9692
Train AUPRC: 0.9723, AUROC: 0.9826, ACC: 0.9484
Early Stopping
root@cc38a5d05d8f:/CGMega#
```

6. Remove the files in folder named `explain/MCF7_CPDB/edge_mask`, `explain/MCF7_CPDB/feature_mask` and `explain/MCF7_CPDB/subgraph` as the preparation for explainable training. Detailed commands are as follows:

